

1 **Therapeutic targeting in breast cancer for the treatment of lung metastasis: ZFP91.**

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6 Metastasis is the major cause of death from cancer and metastasis to the lung in breast cancer is difficult
7 to treat and heterogeneous in nature, complicating its management (1-5). We recently utilized whole
8 transcriptome technologies to define the full complement of differentially expressed kinases and
9 phosphatases in HER2+ breast cancer: in the primary tumor, and in metastasis to the CNS (6-8). Here we
10 utilize whole transcriptome technologies (9, 10) to measure total transcription in the lung metastases of
11 humans with breast cancer, integrating this with transcriptome data from a cell culture model of lung
12 metastatic potential. We identify here a therapeutic target based on its differential expression and
13 up-regulation upon metastasis to the lung in humans with breast cancer, ZFP91, as a candidate
14 therapeutic target for the medical management of lung metastasis.
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We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the transcriptome (RNA), and epigenetic modification (eg., CpG-DNA) of humans with cancer. This includes the primary tumor, the source of the transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - subtypes of the primary tumor, including luminal, basal and HER2+ forms in breast cancer, and adeno and squamous forms of NSCLC in lung cancer, "regional" metastasis to the lymph nodes, metastasis to distant sites, including the lungs, the liver and the brain, and the circulating tumor stem cell. Here we measure total transcription in metastasis to the lungs to discover and describe a therapeutic target identified through rigorous study of the lung metastatic transcriptome in breast cancer: a therapeutic target that is up-regulated and metastasis-specific, providing ideal therapeutic index to minimize toxicity and maximize efficacy: ZFP91.

Results

Figure 1: ZFP91 is differentially expressed in lung metastasis in humans with breast cancer.

I. Lung metastases and primary tumors; human breast cancer.

n=6 primary tumors from humans with breast cancer

n=2 lung metastases (tumor) from humans with breast cancer

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
80829	6.12E-02	0.201	-1.87216	-0.3758515	1509.55	ZFP91	4526/22997	80.3

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors of the breast and in lung metastases of humans with breast cancer (5), we discovered differential expression of ZFP91 zinc finger protein, atypical E3 ubiquitin ligase, encoded by *ZFP91* in metastasis to the lungs in humans with breast cancer (**Chart 1**). The expression of ZFP91 changed more than 80% of the human lung metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 22,997 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of ZFP91 messenger RNA in lung metastases, demonstrating up-regulation of ZFP91 during disease progression and dissemination in breast cancer.

II. Cell culture model of lung metastatic propensity; human breast cancer.

n=2 MDA-PAR lung metastasis cancer cells (MDA-MB-231, low metastatic potential)

n=2 MDA-LM2 lung metastasis cancer cells (MDA-MB-231, high metastatic potential)

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
80829	5.20E-02	0.189	-1.94346	-0.3666896	393.31	ZFP91	926/10554	91.2

Through measurement of total transcription in cells with low metastatic potential as compared to cells with high metastatic potential using the MDA-LM2 model derived from MDA-MB-231 breast cancer cells, we validated differential expression of ZFP91 in metastasis to the lung in breast cancer (**Chart 2**). The expression of ZFP91 here changed more than 90% of the lung metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 10,554 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating higher expression of ZFP91 messenger RNA in breast cancer cells with high potential to metastasize to the lungs, demonstrating viability of ZFP91 as a therapeutic target to manage disease progression and dissemination to the lungs in humans with breast cancer.

1 Thus, differential and increased expression of ZFP91 defines the lung metastatic transcriptome in
2 human breast cancer.

3 **Discussion**

4 Adjunctive treatments in medical oncology limit the emergence of resistant tumor clones during
5 treatment with a second agent (whether neoadjuvantive chemotherapy or a targeted therapy like
6 trastuzumab). Inhibitors of ZFP91, immunoglobulin or small molecule based (once evaluated for toxicity
7 and safety) can immediately be tested for efficacy in patients with lung metastasis who have failed
8 previous treatment, with the ultimate goal of identifying the most effective inhibitors of lung metastasis in
9 humans with breast cancer who have not yet progressed but are at predicted high risk, or those whose
10 metastasis has not yet become unmanageable due to metastasis size, number or location. A multi-kinase
11 approach delivered in conjunction with chemotherapies that target dNTP synthesis, replication of the
12 daughter strand and activity at the spindle at anaphase, targeting *CDKN* inactivation and ATP-binding
13 cassette pump expression in resistant cases, is most likely to be most effective in limiting tumor clone
14 resistance (11).
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Methods

We utilized GSE191230 for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in metastasis to the lungs and in primary tumors from humans with breast cancer (along with GSE186637, in human breast cancer cells for target validation) using RNA-sequencing and microarray data (published and public) and R-based computational methods.